

Identification of Botanical Biomarkers in Argentinian *Diplotaxis*

Honeys: Flavonoids and Glucosinolates

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Analytical Methods.

Abstract

In order to select and establish floral biomarkers of the botanical origin of *Diplotaxis tenuifolia* honeys, the flavonoids and glucosinolates present in bee-deposited nectar collected from the hive combs (not mature honey) and mature-honey from the same hive where the nectar was collected, were analyzed by LC-UV-PAD-ESI-MSn. Flavonol glycosides of kaempferol, quercetin and isorhamnetin were detected and characterized. The *Diplotaxis tenuifolia* honeys contained also aglicones derivatives of kaempferol, quercetin and isorhamnetin. The differences between the phenolic profiles of the honey and nectar could be owed to hydrolytic enzymatic activities. The present work was complemented also with the analysis of aliphatic and indole glucosinolates in nectar and honeys of *Diplotaxis tenuifolia*. This is the first report, to the best of our knowledge, finding glucosinolates as honey constituents. Moreover, these honeys contained different amounts of propolis-derived flavonoid aglycones (1.52-2.40 mg/100 g) and hydroxycinnamic acid derivatives (0.03-1.51 mg/100 g). Taking the flavonoids quercetin, kaempferol and isorhamnetin detected in all samples, together with the glucosinolates also detected in the samples could be useful for establishing complementary biomarkers for the determination of the floral origin of Argentinian *Diplotaxis* honeys.

Keywords: *Diplotaxis tenuifolia*, floral markers, botanical origin, nectar, LC-UV-PAD-ESI-MSn

INTRODUCTION

Unifloral honey is produced from the nectar of one plant species (1). These honeys obtained from identified botanical sources, possess specific composition and could be commonly trade at higher prices than honeys from mixed botanical sources. Therefore, they are considered a premium food product. The identification of floral markers to certify the botanical origin of a given honey is important for correct and legal labelling. In the past decade different compounds have been suggested as floral markers including phenolic compounds as kaempferol, ellagic acid, or the group of myricetin, tricetin and luteolin as identified floral markers for rosemary, heather and eucalyptus honeys respectively (2, 3, 4, 5, 6). All these markers were detected either in the floral nectar directly collected from the flowers or in the content of the bee-honey-sack which has been found particularly useful to study the presence of specific markers for each floral origin. Generally in these nectars, glucosidic conjugates of flavonoid compounds were detected as sophorosides and gentiobiosides. These glucosides of flavonoids are hydrolyzed by the bee enzymes to render the corresponding aglycones that are the metabolites detected in most mature honeys (2, 6). However, in a recent study, different flavonoid rhamnosides and rutinosides were detected in flower nectar, such as kaempferol rhamnosides in acacia honey. These glycosidic compounds can not be hydrolyzed by the glucosidase activity of the bee saliva (6, 7) and no rhamnosidase activity has been reported in bees either. During the elaboration and maturation of the honey in the hive, nectar compounds undergo changes due to oxidation, probably related to the activity of the hydrogen peroxide and the enzymatic activity from the bees.

Diplotaxis tenuifolia is a cruciferous leafy vegetable that contains a wide range of bioactive phytochemicals such as natural antioxidants (vitamin C, carotenoids and phenolics), and specific nitrogen-sulphur compounds specific of cruciferous species, the glucosinolates (8, 9). Glucosinolates are β -thioglucoside N-hydroxysulphates containing a side chain and a β -D glucopyranosyl moiety. The side chain determines whether the glucosinolate is defined as aliphatic, aromatic or indole (10). Glucosinolates are hydrolyzed by the enzyme myrosinase, producing bioactive breakdown products such as isothiocyanates and indoles. These compounds are known to confer the disease-preventive and health-promoting effects of cruciferous foods on human health (11, 12, 13). More than 120 glucosinolates have been identified in *Brassicaceae*, and the concentration and type of glucosinolates may vary depending on the development stages and also in different organs within the plant (leaves, flowers, seed roots). Until now, botanical species giving unifloral honeys in Europe belonging to the *Brassicaceae* family were reported for *Diplotaxis eruroides* (Torner) DC honeys, from different species belonging to the same botanical genus sharing similar characteristics, but in this report, the individual wild cruciferous was considered (14).

Thus, the main objective of this study is the phytochemical fingerprinting of flavonoid glycosides and glucosinolates during the nectar and honeys maturation from *Diplotaxis tenuifolia* L.D. and the stability of, as well as the potential use as floral markers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

“Nectar collection”. *Diplotaxis tenuifolia* LD. C The bees deposits nectar regurgated as liquid spit into the comb, the nectars were collected from the hives.

Honey collection. Three sets honey of samples were obtained from different localities in Bahia Blanca (Argentina). All samples were stored at 4 °C in the dark for further analysis.

Extraction of Markers from Nectar. Phytochemical compounds from six different nectars of *Diploaxis tenuifolia* were isolated after Sep-Pack SPE procedure (Waters Milipore, USA). Briefly, the samples were diluted with ultra pure water (Milli-Q system, Millipore Corp., Bedford, MA), and centrifuged at 5000 g for 10 min, in a Centromix centrifuge (Selecta, Barcelona). The supernatants were filtered through a sep-pack cartridge previously activated with methanol Milli-Q water (10:10, v:v). The compounds that remained adsorbed in the cartridge were eluted with 1 mL of pure methanol. The aqueous phase were lyophilized and re-dissolved in 2 mL of Milli-Q water. All fractions from all the samples were filtered through a 0.45 μ m membrane filter Millex-HV₁₃ (Millipore Corp., USA) and stored at -80° C until further analyzed by LC-UV-PDA-ESI-MSn.

Extraction of Markers from Honey. Analysis of phytochemical compounds was determined according to the methodology reported by [Truchado et al. \(7\)](#), with some modifications. Honey samples (10g) were homogenized in Milli-Q water (1:5, w:v) a pH 2 adjusted with on HCl until completely dissolved. The solutions were then extracted using a Sep-Pack C₁₈ cartridge, which was previously activated as described above. After rinsing the cartridge with 10 mL Milli Q water, the flavonoid fraction eluted by using 2 mL of pure methanol. The aqueous phases were lyophilized and re-dissolved with 2 mL of Milli-Q water, filtered through a 0.45- μ m filter, and stored at -80° C for further LC-UV-PAD-ESI-MSn analysis.

Analysis of Flavonoid Compounds by HPLC-PDA-Tandem Mass Spectrometry (MS-MS). Chromatographic separations of nectars from wild crucifers were carried out in a 250mm×4.6 mm i.d., 5µm, C₁₈ Phenomenex Luna column with a Phenomenex “Securityguard” precolumn with a C₁₈ cartridge (Macclesfield, Cheshire, United Kingdom), using Milli-Q water (A) and pure methanol (B) as solvents (99.9%, HPLC gradient grade; Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). The flavonoids were separated using a linear gradient starting with 0% B at 0–5 min, reaching 17% B at 15–17min, 25% B at 22 min, 35% B at 30 min, 50% B at 35min, 99% B at 50min and at 55–65 min 0% B. The flow rate of 1 mL min⁻¹, and the injection volume 20µL. All chromatograms were recorded at 270 and 330 nm.

The LC-UV-PDA-ESI-MS_n analyses were carried out in an Agilent HPLC 1100 series equipped with a photodiode array detector and mass detector in series (Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany). The HPLC consisted of a binary pump (model G1312A), an autosampler (model G1313A), a degasser (model G1322A), and a photodiode array detector (model G1315B). The HPLC system was controlled by a ChemStation software (Agilent, v. 08.03). The mass detector was an ion trap spectrometer (model G2445A) equipped with an electrospray ionization interface and was controlled by LCMSD software (Agilent, v. 4.1). The ionization conditions were adjusted at 350 °C and 4 kV for capillary temperature and voltage, respectively. The nebulizer pressure and flow rate of nitrogen were 65.0 psi and 11 L min⁻¹, respectively. The full scan mass covered the range from m/z 100 up to m/z 1500. Collision-induced fragmentation experiments were performed in the ion trap using helium as the collision gas, with voltage ramping cycles from 0.3 up to 2V. Mass spectrometry data were acquired in the negative ionization mode. MS_n is carried out in the automatic mode on the more abundant fragment ion in MS (n-1).

The phenolic compounds were identified according to their UV spectra, molecular weights, retention time and their MS-MS fragments, when possible, with commercially available standards. Flavonols as quercetin-rutinoside at 330 nm, flavones as chrysin at 330 nm, and flavanones as hesperedin at 270 nm. All these external standards were purchased from Sigma (St. Louis MO), except chrysin (Carl Roth, OGH, Karlsruhe, Germany).

Analysis of Glucosinolates by HPLC-PAD-Tandem Mass Spectrometry (MS-MS). Analysis of glucosinolates in nectars and honey samples was achieved using the same instruments, and the same column as used for nectar analysis. In this case, the mobile phase was a mixture of (A) Trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) 0.01% and (B) acetonitrile/TFA (99.9:0.01). These compounds were separated and identified by their UV spectra, molecular weight and their characteristic MS fragment ions following a previously reported LC-MS method (15, 16).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Flavonoids in Nectars of *Diplotaxis tenuifolia*. LC-UV-PDA-ESI-MSn screening of five nectars showed similar chromatographic profiles (Figure 1, Table 1). The major compound detected was kaempferol with substituted hydroxyl in the 3 position (6) (UV spectra) (Table 2) (17). Its deprotonated molecular ion at m/z 609 [M-H]⁻ indicated the presence of two hexoses and the MS2 fragmentation showed losses of hexosyl (-162) and hexosyl plus water (-180) from [M-H]⁻, which corresponded to m/z 447 and 429, respectively, with a relative abundance (Table 2), and the deprotonated ion of kaempferol (m/z 285) as base peak. This fragmentation is characteristic of a dihexoside with interglycosidic linkage 1→2 (18). The presence of glucose as the only

hexose in the study of *D. tenuifolia* leaves could be indicative that the compound **6** is kaempferol-3-*O*-sophoroside (kaempferol-3-*O*-(1→2) diglucoside) (19).

The compound **4** is a dihexoside of quercetin which MSⁿ fragmentation is similar to the compound **6** (Figure 1, Table 2). The UV spectrum of compound **4** could not be observed because of coelution in one single chromatographic peak with **5**. All these data, and their retention times (*Rt*) with respect to **6**, suggested that **4** can be tentatively characterized as quercetin-3-*O*-sophoroside. This compound is only detected in trace amounts when is observed. The UV spectra of peak **4+5** corresponded to kaempferol-3-*O*-substituted. In the MS² fragmentation of compound **5** a base peak at *m/z* 285 corresponding to the deprotonated aglycone ion [kaempferol-H]⁻ was observed, ~~indicating that only one phenolic hydroxyl-substituted compound~~ and other minor peak with relative abundance of 20% corresponded to the loss of hexosyl radical (18).

Compounds **1** and **2** (Figure 1, Table 2) coeluted under a single chromatographic peak and the MS analysis showed the correspondence to quercetin and isorhamnetin trihexosides, [M-H]⁻ at *m/z* 787 and 801, respectively. The MS² [787]⁻ and MS³ [787→625]⁻ fragmentations of **1**, showed the ions at *m/z* 625 and 463 as base peaks respectively (Table 2, Figure 2). This fragmentation pattern corresponding to quercetin-3,3',4'-tri-*O*-glucoside was previously described in *D. tenuifolia* leaves (17). This compound was not detected in any of the nectar samples analyzed, instead a compound, which MS² fragmentation corresponded to quercetin-di-*O*-hexoside was observed (glycosylation in different phenolic hydroxyl-positions) (**3**) (Table 1). Compounds **1** and **3** showed the same retention time (*Rt*), which could be indicative that the compound **3** is an artefact generated from **1** in the ion-transfer processes.

The MS² analysis of compound **2** showed at the *m/z* 639 and 477 ions as main peaks and the deprotonated aglycone ion [Aglc-H]⁻ in minor abundance (Table 2,

Figure 3). These results pointed out the glycosylation on two phenolic hydroxyls. In a previous study on leaves of *Diplotaxis spp.*, these flavonols were identified as having a free hydroxyl group at position 7, suggesting that in the glycosylation was at 3- and 4'-positions of the flavonoid nucleus (19). Nevertheless, in the MS3 [801→639] fragmentation (**Figure 3**), the absence of any other fragment ions, indicates the presence of an interglycosidic linkage (1→6) suggesting that in this case, **2** could be isorhamnetin-3-*O*-glucoside-4'-*O*-gentiobioside.

The compounds **7**, **8** and **9** showed the characteristic UV spectra of flavonols with free hydroxyl at position 3. Compound **7** showed a deprotonated molecular ion at m/z 639 and its MS2 fragmentation showed one only peak corresponding to the deprotonated aglycon ion m/z 315. This result indicates that this compound is a gentiobioside. The position of the glycosilation could be in 4', therefore, the structure of this compound **7** can be tentatively characterized as isorhamnetin-4'-*O*-gentiobioside (19). The compounds **8** and **9** were identified as isorhamnetin and kaempferol monohexosides, respectively. These compounds could be labeled as isorhamnetin-4'-*O*-glucoside and kaempferol-4'-*O*-glucoside. The UV spectra, MS and *Rt* for compound **12** suggest us that is a kaempferol aglycone. Some nectar samples obtained from *Diplotaxis* flowers be analysed in the future to confirm the flavonoid glucoside profiles detected in this study.

Flavonoids in the *Diplotaxis tenuifolia* honeys. The LC-PDA chromatogram of methanolic extracts from *Diplotaxis* honeys revealed the presence the quercetin (**11**), kaempferol (**12**) and isorhamnetin (**17**) in all samples (**Figure 4**). In previous works about the occurrence of flavonoids and glucosinolates in different *Brassica spp*, these flavonol aglycones were detected in leaves, roots and also flowers (8, 19, 20, 21, 22). However, this is the first time that these types of compounds are studied in honeys from

wild cruciferous plants. Flavonoid glucosides present in nectar were not detected in the mature-honey (**Figure 4**). These results are in agreement with previous studies, where the flavonoid glucosides present in nectar are hydrolyzed to give the corresponding aglycons by the activity of hydrolytic glucosidases in the bee saliva and/or in the honey (2, 6). Moreover, during honey elaboration/ripening the nectar flavonoid profile can be modified by the action of bee saliva glucosidases and oxidant conditions (hydrogen peroxide) in the hive (7). This phenomenon could explain the occurrence of kaempferol, isorhamnetin and quercetin in *Diplotaxis* honey while nectar contained their flavonoid glucosides (2, 6). However, isorhamnetin 4` diglucoside (7) is present in different proportions in two of the analysed honey samples (data no show). This variability could suggest a different degree of ripening in every honey sample. Quercetin (11), kaempferol (12) and isorhamnetin (17) are main phenolic metabolites present in honey. However, those compounds are derived from the propolis, which are incorporated into beeswax and honey. When comparing the flavonoid profile of *Diplotaxis* honey to those of Argentinian propolis, the main difference is that these compounds are much more relevant in honey than in propolis. Therefore, these three flavonoids could be used as chemical markers for this botanical origin.

Glucosinolates in the Nectars and Honeys of *Diplotaxis tenuifolia*. The study of MS²[M-H]⁻ fragmentation of the aqueous extracts of nectars and honeys showed different glucosinolate peaks corresponding to specific product ions at *m/z* 259 and 97 which correspond to the fragment ions from the aglycone side chain and to the sulphate group, respectively, glucosinolate marker-ions as reported elsewhere (**Figure 5 and 6**) (16, 20, 23). The glucosinolates detected in the nectar samples were the aliphatic glucoiberin (*m/z* 422) and glucoraphanin (*m/z* 436). The glucosinolate identified as

glucobrassicinapin (m/z 386), also aliphatic, was detected in the nectar samples too. For the indolic group of glucosinolates, the 4-hydroxyglucobrassicin (m/z 463), glucobrassicin (m/z 447), and the neoglucobrassicin (m/z 477), were all present in the nectar samples. The structures identified of the glucosinolates were confirmed according to their R_t , UV-spectra at 227 nm, molecular masses, MS/MS fragmentation as well as characteristic product ions cited above (16, 20, 23, 24) (Table 3).

Glucoraphanin and glucoerucin were described as chemotaxonomic markers of *Diplotaxis tenuifolia* (8, 20, 25). Except for glucoerucin, undetected in our samples, we found the glucoraphanin and the glucoiberin, as well as indolic compounds (glucobrassicin, neoglucobrassicin) also present in other related plant species as *Eruca vesicaria*. The glucobrassicinapin, common glucosinolate of *Brassica spp.* (i.e., *B. rapa*, *B. napus*) (16, 26), was also detected in the samples. Eventhough, multiple accessions of *D. tenuifolia* were characterized by the absence the 4-hydroxyglucobrassicin (26), this glucosinolate was reported in the plant (8, 15, 20) and also found in our nectars. These results could indicate the floral origin of the *D. tenuifolia* nectars, according to the glucosinolate profile in addition to the information obtained from the phenolic compounds.

In the study of LC-UV-PAD-ESI-MSⁿ of the aqueous extract in (mature) honey the aliphatic glucosinolates glucoiberin and the glucosinolate identified as glucobrassicinapin were detected. Indolic glucosinolates are known to be chemically less stable than aliphatic glucosinolates (8, 11, 25) and, during the maturation of nectar to honey in the hive, the indolic glucosinolates could be degraded to isothiocyanates, indoles and other unstable compounds as a result of the action of glucohydrolases as well as non-enzymatic conversion to other products. The indolic glucosinolates could be more affected by abiotic stresses and changes upon different environmental conditions

during maturation or storage of the honey, which could explain how the glucosinolate composition varied with losses of the more sensitive compounds (8, 11, 12). Therefore, the presence or absence of these nitrogen-sulphur compounds might be used as bioindication of freshness of a given honey.

This is the first report, to the best of our knowledge, of glucosinolates being detected and identified in nectar and honey produced from *D.s tenuifolia* plants. Although, the quantification of the glucosinolate concentration was not possible in the limited amount of available samples.

Propolis-Derived Flavonoids in the Nectars and Honeys of *Diplotaxis tenuifolia*.

The UV chromatograms at 330 nm from nectars or honeys showed a similar phenolic fingerprint (**Figure 1** and **Figure 4**). The profiles were similar to the obtained from propolis samples originally of Northern Argentina, characterized by the presence of phenolic acids and flavonoid aglycones (27, 28). The flavanones pinocembrin, pinobanksin-acetate and pinostrobin, the flavones chrysin and tectochrysin, and the phenolic acid, dimethyl-allyl-caffeate were detected in all honey samples in different amounts, as shown in **Table 4**. The presence of these compounds in the different honey samples and nectars of *-Diplotaxis* honeys is quite variable because it depends on the degree of propolis contamination in the hive and beeswax (29, 30). This finding is of great interest because it suggests that the propolis-derived flavonoids are transferred to the honey from the nectar droplets deposited into the hive (**Figure 1**).

As conclusive remarks, we could highlight that the phytochemical profiling of flavonoid-*O*-glucosides of kaempferol, quercetin and isorhamnetin detected in nectars and honeys of *D. tenuifolia* as well as the corresponding aglycones of these flavonoids,

together with the differences in abundance and composition of aliphatic and indole glucosinolates in nectars and honeys could represent a potential tool of chemical markers for the determination of the botanical origin of 'Argentinian honeys'.

The certification of the floral origin of the honey is a very important task to further guarantee the quality to the consumer and the authenticity of the honey.

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Figure Captions.

Figure 1. UV chromatogram of *Diplotaxis tenuifolia* nectar at 330 nm. **1**, Quercetin-3,3',4'-tri-*O*-Glucoside; **2**, Isorhamnetin-3-*O*-Glucoside-4'-*O*-diGlucoside; **3**, Quercetin-3,4'-di-*O*-Glucoside; **4**, Quercetin-3-*O*-diGlucoside; **5**, Kaempferol-3-*O*-diGlucoside isomer; **6**, Kaempferol-3-*O*-diGlucoside; **7**, Isorhamnetin-4'-*O*-diGlucoside; **8**, Isorhamnetin-4'-*O*-Glucoside; **9**, Kaempferol-4'-*O*-Glucoside; **10**, Pinobanksin; **11**, Quercetin; **12**, Kaempferol; **13**, Chrysin; **14**, Pinocembrin; **15** Pinostrobin, **16**, Dimethyl-allyl-caffeate; **17**, Isorhamnetin.

Figure 2. MS2 spectrum of Quercetin-3,3', 4'-tri-*O*-glucoside (compound **1**)

Figure 3. MS2 spectrum of Isorhamnetin-3-*O*-glucoside-4'-*O*-gentiobioside (compound **2**)

Figure 4. UV chromatogram of *Diplotaxis tenuifolia* honey at 330 nm. **10**, Pinobanksin; **11**, Quercetin; **12**, Kaempferol; **13**, Chrysin; **14**, Pinocembrin; **15** Pinostrobin, **16**, Dimethyl-allyl-caffeate; **17**, Isorhamnetin; **18**, Pinocembrin-3-acetate; **19**, Tectochrysin.

Figure 5. EIC of glucosinolates in aqueous phase from nectar of *Diplotaxis tenuifolia*.

Figure 6. MS/MS product ion spectra of glucosinolates in nectar *Diplotaxis tenuifolia*.

Table 1. Phenolic compounds contents in *Diplotaxis tenuifolia* nectars from different zone ^a.

Peaks	Compounds	1	2	4	5	6
1+2+3	Querc-3,3',4'-triGlc ¹ + Isrhm-3-Glc-4'diGlc+ Querc-3,4'-diGlc	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001
4+5	Querc-3-diGlc+ Kaempf-3-diGlc isomer	0.005	0.004	0.006	0.006	0.007
5	Kaempf-3-diGlc isomer	-	-	0.009	0.008	0.009
6	Kaempf-3-diGlc	0.007	0.005	0.003	0.003	0.003
7	Isrhm-4'-diGlc	0.003	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001
8	Isrhm-4'-Glc	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001
9	Kaempf-4'-Glc	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001
11	Quercetin	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001
12	Kaempferol	0.003	0.002	0.004	0.004	0.004
13	Chrysin	0.002	0.000	0.002	0.002	0.002
10	Pinobanksin	0.005	0.003	0.005	0.007	0.006
12	Pinocembrin	0.006	0.006	0.003	0.001	0.006
13	Pinostrobin	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
16	Dimethylalylcaffate	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001

^a Values are mg/100g of nectar. -, not detected; tr, trazas

¹ Glc; Glycoside

Table 2. Rt; UV, MS: [M-H]⁻ and -MS2[M-H]⁻ data of flavonoids from nectar from *Diplotaxis tenuifolia*.¹

Compounds ²	Rt (min)	UV (nm)	[M-H] ⁻	-MS2[M-H] ⁻ (m/z) (%)			
				-162	-180	-324	[Aglc-H/2H] ⁻
1 Querc-3,3',4'-triGlc ³	22.3	255, 267sh, 353 ⁴	787	625(100)		463(10)	
2 Isrhmn-3-Glc-4'-diGlc ³	22.3	255, 267sh, 353 ⁴	801	639(96)		477(100)	315(33)
3 Querc-3,4'-diGlc	22.3	255, 267sh, 353 ⁴	625	463(100)			301(30)
4 Querc-3-diGlc	23.1	---- ⁵	625	463(10)	445(27)		300(100)
5 Kaempf-3-diGlc isomer	23.1	265, 295sh, 347 ⁵	609	447(20)			285(100)
6 Kaempf-3-diGlc	25.6	265, 299sh, 347	609	447(6)	429(60)		285(100)
7 Isrhmn-4'-diGlc	27.1	255, 267sh, 370	639				315(100)
8 Isrhmn-4'-Glc	28.2	255, 266sh, 325sh, 365	477				315(100)
9 Kaempf-4'-Glc	28.3.0	267, 315sh, 363	447				285(100)
10 Pinobanksin	34.9						
11 Quercetin	35.1						
12 Kaempferol	38.2	253sh, 267, 300sh, 320sh, 367	285				
13 Chrysin	41.9	267, 313	253				
14 Pinocembrin	42.1	289, 331sh	255				
15 Pinostrobin	42.3	293, 333sh	269				
16 Dimethylallylcaffeate	40.3		247				

¹ Main observed fragments. Other ions were found but they have not been included.

² Isrhmn: isorhamnetin (3,5,7,4'-tetrahydroxy-3'-methoxyflavone); Querc: quercetin (3,5,7,3',4'-pentahydroxyflavone); Kaempf: kaempferol (3,5,7,4'-tetrahydroxyflavone); Chrysin (5,7-dihydroxyflavone); Pinocembrin (5,7-dihydroxyflavanone); Pinostrobin (5-hydroxy-7-methoxyflavanone).

³ MS3[787→625]⁻: 463(100); MS3[787→463]⁻: 301(100). MS3[801→639]⁻: 315(100); MS3[801→477]⁻: 315(100).

⁴ UV spectra de **1+2+3**

⁵ Compound **4** and **5** coeluted, el UV spectra observado es el del **5**.

Table 3. List of identified glucosinolates with the corresponding retention times and MS data.

Compounds	Rt (min)	[M-H]⁻	MS2[M-H]⁻, m/z
Nectar			
Glucoiberin	3.0	422	358, 259
Glucoraphanin	4.0	436	375, 294, 259
4-Hydroxyglucobrassicin	11.7	463	
Glucobrassicinapin	15.0	386	285, 259
Glucobrassicin	16.8	447	275, 259, 251
Neoglucobrassicin	24.6	477	477, 466, 284, 259
Honey			
Glucoiberin	3.0	422	358, 259
Glucobrassicinapin	15.0	386	285, 259

Table 4. Phenolic compounds contents in *Diplotaxis tenuifolia* honeys ^a.

Flavonoids					
Peaks	Compounds	tr	D-01	D-02	D-03
	Isorhamnetin-4'-Glc	28.1	0.67±0.07	0.31±0.07	nd
10	Pinobanksin	35.0	0.07±0.00	0.22±0.00	0.74±0.05
11	Quercetin	35.1	0.17±0.05	0.33±0.07	0.19±0.00
12	Kaempferol	37.8	0.62±0.01	0.65±0.10	0.21±0.03
17	Isorhamnetin	38.09	0.26±0.00	0.10±0.03	0.11±0.00
13	Chrysin	40.36	0.05±0.00	0.05±0.01	0.08±0.01
14	Pinocembrin	40.7	0.15±0.04	0.13±0.01	0.10±0.01
15	Pinostrobin	41.1	0.09±0.02	0.07±0.02	0.06±0.00
18	Pinobanksin -3-acetate	41.8	0.01±0.00	tr	tr
19	Tectochrysin	42.3	0.02±0.00	0.01±0.00	0.01±0.00
Total			2.40	1.65	1.52
Hidroxicinnamic Acids					
OH1	Chlorogenic acid	19.9	-	0.04±0.01	0.25±0.02
OH2	Caffeic acid derivatives	22.5	-	-	0.17±0.02
OH3	p-coumaric acid	26.2	-	-	0.26±0.01
OH4	Caffeic acid derivatives	27.3	-	0.03±0.00	0.24±0.01
OH5	Ferulic acid	28.6	0.02±0.00	-	0.58±0.01
16	Dimethyl-allyl-cafeate	40.4	0.01±0.00	0.21±0.06	0.02±0.02
Total			0.03	0.27	1.51

^a Values are mg/100g of honey. nd, not detected; tr, trazas

1 Figure 1

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39 Figure 2
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Figure 5

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Figure 6

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